

Stroke: Risks, Diagnosis & Prevention

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ABSTRACT: Stroke is been seen as life threatening condition which is caused due to interrupted blood flow to the brain which in turn lead to very saviour complication or death. In this paper we are going to explore stroke type, causes, risk factor, symptoms, diagnosis and treatment of stroke in terms of allopathic and homeopathic approach. Highlighting the importance of early diagnosis, prevention and post stroke care and prevention to improve patient outcome.

KEYWORDS: Diagnosis & Prevention of stroke, Risks.

INTRODUCTION

STROKE is a medical condition which indicate sudden problem in blood flow of the brain i.e. blood supply to the part of brain is reduced blocking brain tissue from receiving oxygen and nutrients, due to which within a minuit brain cells be gain to die.hence this lead into causes, symptoms, treatment and diagnosis, providing a good understanding of this life threatening condition known as stroke.

Epidemiology and Prevalence

It is seen that stroke is second most leading cause of disability and death across the globe. As per World Health Organisation(WHO) 15 million people are affected by it out of which 5 million are death and another 5million are facing disability. Stroke is mostly common in individual over 65 years of age, cases in stroke are rising in younger age group due to changes in lifestyle and and increase in factors like diabetics and hypertension. Factor which are affecting stroke incident world wide are genetic predispositions, economic inequality, health care access and urbanisation, hence these conditions enforce a significant through health care cost and lost productivity. early diagnosis, effective prevention and treatment plays critical role in minimising the impact of stroke.

TYPE AND CAUSE OF STROKE

There are various type of stroke, one stroke which is caused either by blocked artery known as ischemic stroke or due to busting and leaking of blood vessel known as hemorrhagic stroke. Some people might have experience a temporary interruption of blood flow to brain known as transient ischemic attack (TIA)which might not cause long lasting symptoms.

➤ ISCHEMIC STROKE

This stroke account for 87% of all stroke which occurs when the arteries going to the brain are narrowed and blocked hence reducing a blood flow known as ischemia. The main causes are:

- **Thrombotic Stroke:-**

This stroke occurs when thrombus is formed in any of the arteries which are supplying blood to the brain. Fatty deposition in the arteries and reduced blood flow (atherosclerosis)and any other artery condition lead to thrombotic stroke.

- **Embolic Stroke:-**

It refers to a clot is formed away from your brain mainly in your heart which is carried throughout your bloodstream and get trapped in the brain narrow arteries. This type of blood clot is called embolus.

➤ HEMORRHAGIC STROKE

It it occurs when the blood vessel in the brain gets ruptured . Main cause of this stroke is hypertension, over usages of blood thinner (anticoagulants), trauma. Thera are two main types:

- **Intracerebral Hemorrhage (ICH):-**
Bleeding directly into the brain tissue which for mshematoma. This increased intracranial pressure compress near by brain structure and leads to secondary injury.
- **Subarachnoid Hemorrhage (SAH):-**
In this bleeding occur in the subarachnoid space due to aneurysm rupture.

➤ TRANSIENT ISCHEMIC ATTACK (TIA)

It is generally referred to a mini stroke which is temporary blockage of blood flow to the brain. Although it is resolved within 24 hours due to which it is served as a warning sign for all the future stroke. hence it is important to recognised TIA for preventing a future stroke.

➤ CRYPTOGENIC STROKE

Mostly a blood clot that blocks flow of blood to the brain causes stroke and we are not able to identify the cause despite medical testing I known as cryptogenic stroke.

➤ BRAIN STEM STROKE

This stroke happens in brainstem hence both side of the body are affected, leaving the person in locked state due to which patient generally are not able to speak or move the body parts below neck and faces difficulty in breathing also.

RISK FACTOR ASSOCIATED WITH STROKE

There are two type of risk factor associated with stroke and understanding these risk factor is really important for both the case of primary and secondary stroke prevention I which highlights the importance of the targeted lifestyle and pharmacological intervention.

➤ MODIFIABLE RISK FACTORS

- **Hypertension:** High blood pressure which accelerates vascular damage and lead to both ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes.
- **Hyperlipidemia:** Increased lipid levels lead to atherosclerotic plaque.
- **Diabetes:** hyperglycaemia increases the risk of micro and macro vascular complications.
- **Obesity:** Obesity in combination to sedentary lifestyle are linked to metabolic syndrome which in turn increase the risk of stroke.
- **Smoking:** Excessive tobacco uses increase chances of clot formation.
- **Atherosclerosis:** If fat and plaque is formed in the arteries it lead to thrombotic stroke due to which blood vessel narrow and risk of blockage increases.
- **Alcohol:** Excessive alcohol and consumption induced to narrowing of blood vessel and lead to stroke.

➤ NON MODIFIABLE RISK FACTORS

- **Genetic predispositions:** Family history of stroke or cardiovascular disease increase chances of stroke.
- **Age:** Risk of stroke increase with increasing age.
- **Gender:** generally males have higher probability of having stroke whereas women's may experience more senior outcomes.
- **Ethnicity:** stroke risk is higher with African and south Asian populations due to combination genetically and environmental factors.

SYMPTOMS OF STROKE

It is really important to understand symptoms of the stroke for early recognition and immediate treatment hence minimising irreversible brain damage. The acronym FAST is used to identify the stroke warning signs:

F- Face drooping: It indicate that any one side of the face feel numb i.

A-Arm weakness: It indicate numbness or weakness in any one arm.

S- Speech difficulty: It indicate difficulty in understanding speech i.e. slurred or confused speaking

T- Time to call emergency services

Other common symptom are:

- One side of body is paralysed.
- Facing trouble in seeing any one eye or both eyes and blurred vision
- Severe headache
- Dizziness which result in trouble in walking, lack of coordination and balance
- Disturbed mental status due to increase intracranial pressure.

DIAGNOSIS OF STROKE

If patient show symptoms of the stroke or TIA then rapid diagnosis is very important for the management of the stroke. There are several method used to diagnosed stroke which include:

➤ Physical examination:-

- Doctor check for symptoms of stroke.
- Patient complete medical history.
- Neurological examination.

➤ Imagine Test:-

- **Non- Contracted Computed Tomography (CT scan)**– It is a first-line imagine which is highly effective in identifying hemorrhagic stroke also shows bleeding in brain, a tumour and other conditions.
- **Magnetic Resonance Imagine (MRI)** –It helps in detecting brain tissue damage in early ischemic stroke and haemorrhages.
- **CT Angiography (CTA) and MR Angiography (MRA)** –These technique allow detailed visualisation of cerebral vascular hence forth helping in identification of aneurysm and abnormalities in blood vessel development which can affect arteries, vein, capillaries and lymphatic in the body including brain.

➤ Laboratory Investigation:-

- **Blood Tests:-**
 - **Complete blood count (CBC)**-Helps in identifying infection and clotting disorders.
 - **Coagulation Profile (PT/INR, aPTT)**- It is important for thrombosis evaluation.
 - **Lipid profile and HbA1c** –It helps in evaluating metabolic risk factors.
- **Electrocardiograph (ECG) :-** It is used to detect cardiac rhythm issue such as atrial fibrillation, which causes stroke.
- **Echocardiogram:-** It helps to identify sources of the clot in the heart that might have travelled to the brain and cause stroke.

Timely diagnosed in combination to physical test, imagine test and laboratory examination help us in identifying the stroke sub type which in turn lead us to the proper therapeutic approach.

Treatment of Stroke

Treatment for stroke depends on the type of stroke and the severity of the condition. Immediate emergency care is aimed at minimising brain damage.

➤ Allopathic treatment for stroke

● Ischemic Stroke Treatment:-

- **Thrombolytic therapy**– Tissue plasminogen activator is a drug used to dissolve blood clot and should be monitored within 4.5 hours of stroke.
- **Mechanical Thrombectomy** – It is a procedure which is used to remove clot by using a catheter usually perform in 24 hours of symptoms onset.
- **Anticoagulant and Antiplatelets** – These are the drugs such as aspirin, heparin, and warfarin which can prevent new clot from forming.
- **Carotid Endarterectomy**-It is a surgery which removes plaque from carotid arteries.

- **Hemorrhagic Stroke Treatment:-**

- **Blood Pressure Management-** In this medication like beta-blockers or calcium channel blocker helps to console blood pressure hence reduced bleeding risk.
- **Surgical Intervention-** Some of the procedures such as craniotomy or aneurysm clipping might be I'm-to stop bleeding.
- **Endovascular Procedure-** It is a procedure where coiling or embolization is done to repair the damage blood vessel.

- **Homeopathic treatment for stroke:-**

Homeopathy has offered a complementary approach towards stroke recovery. This treatment is used mostly during rehabilitation phase for chronic management. Some commonly used homeopathic medicine are

- **Arnica Montana** which is useful for stroke patient experiencing paralysis, weakness or busting sensation.
- **Baryta Carbonica** is prescribed to patients with early stroke symp such as memo loss and speech difficulties.
- **Causticum** is used when there is case of paralysis, particularly muscular weakness and difficulty in speech.
- **Lachesis** is beneficial for post stroke complication such as blood clotting disorder.
- **NuxVomica** is used for stroke patients who are having neurological symptoms including muscle stiffness and digestive issue.
- **Belladonna** is used with high fever and throbbing headaches factors which contribute to stroke.
- **Aconitine Napellusis** used sometimes in the early stage of stroke where there is sudden exposure to a stressful event.

Post Stroke Condition and Prevention

It is seen that after stroke patient suffer from various complication and long term effects,

- Paralysis or weakness in side of the body.
- Difficulty in coordination and balancing.
- Difficulty in speaking or understanding language and slurred speech.
- Memory loss, poor concentration and problem solving skills
- Post stroke fatigue, depression, anxiety and mood swings.
- Increase in thee risk of choking or aspiration pneumonia.
- Constipation and irregular urine.
- Muscle stiffness, contraction and nerve pain.
- Post stroke epilepsy.

Stroke Prevention

- Controlling hypertension, diabetes and cholesterol.
- Main tending healthy lifestyles such as regular exercise avoiding tobacco and alcohol usages.
- Taking all the medication prescribed by doctors.

CONCLUSION

Stroke is a serious medical condition which require immediate medical attention. If people around are aware of the preventive measures, symptoms and risk factor involved then theris of stroke can be reduced. Early intervention and rehabilitation plays major role in enhancing recovery and quality life of stroke survivors. Additionally homeopathic medicine act as supportive treatment hence helping in recovery and symptoms management.

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